

SOP-CELL-014 V1.1

Title: Standard Operating Procedure for Thawing, Passaging, and Cryopreserving RAW 264.7 Cells.

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1 Purpose

This SOP provides standardized procedures for thawing, maintaining, passaging, and cryopreserving RAW 264.7 macrophage-like cells. The goal is to ensure reproducibility, traceability, and compliance with BSL-2 laboratory standards.

2 Background

RAW 264.7 is a murine macrophage-like cell line derived from a BALB/c mouse Abelson leukemia virus-induced tumor. The line is widely used for immunological, phagocytic, and signaling studies. RAW 264.7 cells exhibit semi-adherent growth and can differentiate under stress or prolonged culture conditions.

3 Safety Precautions

- All work under BSL-2 conditions.
- Wear lab coat, gloves, and eye protection as required.
- All waste (media, tips, tubes, flasks) must be autoclaved before disposal.
- Liquid waste must be inactivated with disinfectant prior to autoclaving.
- Disinfect biosafety cabinet and equipment before and after procedures with 70% ethanol.

4 Definitions & Abbreviations

Definitions	Abbreviations
BSL-2	Biosafety Level 2
DMEM	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium
FBS	Fetal Bovine Serum
PBS	Phosphate-Buffered Saline
Cryomedium	90% FBS + 10% DMSO
Passage	Transfer of cells to a new culture vessel to avoid over-confluence
Viability	Percentage of live cells after a procedure (ATP assay, SOP-CELLVIABILITY-003)
QC	Quality Control

5 Materials & Equipment

5.1 Media

- **Culture medium (Cul- RAW 264.7):**
 - Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), high glucose; Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH, Dreieich, Germany
 - 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS); Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany
 - 1% Penicillin (10 U/mL) / Streptomycin (10 µg/mL); Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH, Dreieich, Germany
- **Cryomedium (Cry- RAW 264.7)**
 - DMEM; Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH, Dreieich, Germany
 - 10% Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO); Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH, Dreieich, Germany
 - 20% FBS; Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany

5.2 Consumables

- 1xPhosphate Buffered Saline (PBS); Roth, Karlsruhe, Germany
- Trypsin/EDTA; Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH, Dreieich, Germany
- 100 mm dishes; Corning; Sarstedt; Nümbrecht, Germany
- 15 mL and 50 mL Falcon tubes; Corning
- Serological pipettes (5 mL, 10 mL); Sarstedt, Nümbrecht, Germany
- Pipette tips (10 µL, 100 µL, 1000 µL); Eppendorf AG, Hamburg, Germany
- Cryovials; Nunc, Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH, Dreieich, Germany

5.3 Equipment

- Biosafety cabinet, ESCO Infinity® Classic II; Biomedis Laborservice GmbH, Gießen, Germany
- CO₂ incubator HERAcell 150i; Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH, Dreieich, Germany
- Centrifuges (Eppendorf 5424, 5804; Eppendorf AG, Hamburg, Germany)
- Controlled-rate freezing container (Mr. Frosty™; Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH, Dreieich, Germany)
- Liquid nitrogen storage tank (Taylor-Wharton, distributor dependent)
- Autoclave (Variomag®, Hudson, USA)

6 Procedures

Note: RAW 264.7 cells are semi-adherent and should not be over-trypsinized. Detachment is performed mechanically using PBS and a sterile cell scraper.

6.1 Thawing and Adapting Cells

1. Pre-warm complete medium to **37 °C**.
2. Retrieve cryovial from liquid nitrogen (keep on ice) and thaw rapidly in a **37 °C water bath** (keep cap above waterline).
3. Disinfect vial exterior with 70% ethanol.
4. Transfer contents into a 15 mL tube containing **5 mL pre-warmed medium**.
5. Centrifuge at **500×g for 4 min at RT**.
6. Discard supernatant; resuspend pellet in **10 mL fresh medium**.
7. Seed into a **10 cm dish** and label (cell line, passage, date, operator).
8. Incubate at **37 °C, 5% CO₂**.
9. Do not change the medium within the first 24 h.
10. Do not change the medium within the first 24 h. No experiments until passage +3.
11. **QC₁**: Microscopically inspect for attachment/morphology after 24 h.
12. **QC₂**: For viability confirmation, refer to SOP-CELLVIABILITY-003 V1.1.

Waste: Collect all consumables and waste liquid; autoclave before disposal.

6.2 Passaging Cells

1. Passage at **60–80% confluence** or when a dense cell layer is visible.
2. Remove culture medium and wash **once with PBS**.
3. Detach cells using **PBS and gentle scraping**; avoid trypsinization.
4. Transfer suspension to a 15 mL tube and centrifuge at **500×g for 5 min**.
5. Discard supernatant; resuspend in fresh medium.
6. Split culture **1:3 to 1:5**, typically **twice per week**.
7. Seed into new culture vessels; label with cell line, passage, date, operator.
8. **QC₁**: Microscopically inspect for attachment/morphology after 24 h.

Waste: Medium and PBS washes must be autoclaved.

6.3 Cryopreserving Cells

1. Harvest cells at 80–90% confluence.
2. Count cells using Trypan Blue with hemocytometer or automated counter.
3. **QC₁**: For viability confirmation, refer to SOP-CELLVIABILITY-003 V1.1. Only viable cells are used.
4. Pellet 1.0×10^6 viable cells per cryovial at $500 \times g$, 5 min.
5. Resuspend pellet in 1 mL cryomedium (**90% FBS + 10% DMSO**).
6. Aliquot 1 mL per cryovial.
7. Freeze at -80 °C overnight in controlled-rate container ($\sim -1 \text{ °C/min}$).
8. Transfer vials to liquid nitrogen the following day.

Waste: Autoclave all waste material.

7 Acceptance Criteria

- **Thawing:** Cells reach $\geq 70\%$ confluence within 4 days post-thaw, normal morphology.
- **Passaging:** Only cultures at 70-80% confluence, without contamination or abnormal morphology, are passaged.
- **Cryopreservation:** Only cells with $>90\%$ viability are frozen; vials must be properly labeled.
- COS-7 cultures must not be used beyond passage number 20; for continued work, new cultures must be re-established from cryopreserved stocks.

8 Deviations / Troubleshooting

If cells show abnormal morphology, reduced viability, or any signs of contamination, the experiment must not be initiated. Such cultures must be terminated immediately, disposed of according to BSL-2 waste management procedures, and the laboratory supervisor must be informed without delay.

8.1 Failure to Proliferate After Thawing

- Inspect morphology microscopically.
- Perform viability test (ATP assay, SOP-CELLVIABILITY-003).
 - **Negative:** Autoclave and discard culture.
 - **Positive:** Replace medium, monitor for 48 h.
- If still no growth, autoclave and discard; thaw new vial; document batch number.

8.2 Bacterial or Fungal Contamination

- Stop work immediately.
- autoclave contaminated vessels and Discard disinfect material and clean bench with UV disinfection program (see SOP- BSL-2 SAFETY_ GUIDELINES-001 V4.2)
- Decontaminate biosafety cabinet, incubator, water baths, pipettes. Replace incubator water (with CuSO_4 or thymol).
- Record contamination in lab book and inform supervisor.

9 Documentation

- Record all procedures in hardcopy lab book: date, passage, medium lot, operator, observations.
- Complete checklist/form sheet for thawing, passaging, cryopreservation.
- Capture photographic documentation of cells after thawing.

10 References

1. Internal reference SOP (HeLa structure): SOP-CELL-012 V1.3
2. Internal viability SOP (ATP-based assay): **SOP-CELLVIABILITY-003 V1.x**
3. Internal BSL-2 safety guidelines: **SOP-BSL-2-SAFETY-GUIDELINES-00x**
4. ATCC TIB-71: RAW 264.7 Cell Line Data Sheet
5. DSMZ ACC 313: Cell Line Information